

(pK_1 in BPGR and pK_1 and pK_2 in NRS) in these ligands could not be obtained under the present conditions of study.

Absorption spectra and composition of the chelate : Three series of solutions in different ratios of metal : ligand (1:1, 1:4 and 4:1) were prepared and the acid concentration of these solutions was adjusted from pH 1.0 to pH 2.0 in all the cases. The absorption spectra was then recorded in the entire visible range. pH values above 2.0 could not be adjusted due to the hydrolysis of hafnium.

In the present case, Hf forms only one 2:1 (M:L) chelate with BPGR in the pH range of 1.2 to 1.8 having λ_{max} 520nm. However, the detailed study of this chelate was done at pH 1.8 and at 530 nm at which the difference in absorbance between the chelate and the ligand is maximum.

Similarly in case of NRS, at pH 1.5, λ_{max} shifts from 370 nm to 390 nm and remains the same upto pH 2.0. Above pH 2.0 a further shift in λ_{max} (400 nm) occurs. In the present work the first chelate was studied at pH 1.5 and at 430 nm. The other chelate expected to form above pH has been found to be unstable and hence could not be studied in detail.

Study of equilibrium : BPGR Chelate : The formation of 2:1 Hf: BPGR) chelate of hafnium with BPGR at pH 1.8 is complete within 10 mins. At this pH, the involvement of hydrolyzed species of hafnium, $[Hf(OH)]^{3+}$ may be considered for chelate formation.

The reaction thus, becomes,

The equilibrium constant, K, of the above reaction and the conditional stability constant, β , of the complex are related as follows :

$$\log \beta = -4 \log [H]^+ + \log K$$

Thus a plot of $\log \beta$ vs. $\log [H]^+$ should give a slope equal to -4.0 which is the number of protons liberated according to reaction (i). The intercept is equal to $\log K$, the equilibrium constant.

The values of β can be calculated at different acid concentrations (Table 1) by the methods reported earlier^{2,5}.

The values of $\log \beta$ are evaluated in this way and plotted against $\log [H]^+$, which gives a straight line. The value of the slope is equal to -3.8 (about 4) which is the number of protons liberated during reaction (i). The intercept is equal to 16.1 which is the $\log K$, the equilibrium constant of the reaction. Reaction (i) appears, therefore, to be correct with the $[Hf(OH)]^{3+}$ species participating in the complexation reaction.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF CONDITIONAL STABILITY CONSTANT OF BPGR CHELATE AT 530 nm*

pH	Absorbance of stoichiometric mixture	$Q \times 10^5$	$\beta \times 10^{-9}$	$\log [H]^+$	$\log \beta$
1.2	0.600	4.691	397.300	-1.2	11.5992
1.3	0.590	4.536	113.500	-1.3	11.0551
1.4	0.580	4.382	61.790	-1.4	10.7908
1.5	0.570	4.229	23.050	-1.5	10.3628
1.6	0.560	4.074	12.820	-1.6	10.1081
1.7	0.550	3.765	4.996	-1.7	9.6986
1.8	0.540	3.456	2.348	-1.8	9.3707

* Final conc. of $Hf^{4+}(A_T) = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ and of BPGR (B_T) = $0.50 \times 10^{-4} M$. Molar extinction coefficient of the chelate (E_C) and the ligand (E_L) at pH 1.8 = 12.40×10^3 and 5.92×10^3 respectively.

Hf-NRS Chelate : The 1:1 chelate formed with NRS is a fast reaction at pH 1.5. Its kinetic and the proton liberation studies could not be done. It was not possible to assume the reacting species of hafnium. Although the chelate has been found to be anionic in nature, its structure could not be suggested on the basis of present studies.

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2-Hydroxy-4-Methylpropiophenone Oxime (HMPOX) as an Analytical Reagent—Studies on Vanadium Chelate

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SEVERAL organic reagents¹⁻⁶ have been proposed for the gravimetric determination of vanadium(V) but very few afford precipitate which can be weighed as such. The present work was undertaken with the

intention to introduce a new ligand for the gravimetric determination of vanadium(V). 2-Hydroxy-4-methylpropiophenone oxime⁷ yields a crystalline brown red precipitate in acidic solution. Precipitation starts at pH 2.0 and is quantitative in the pH range 2.5-4.0. Copper(II) and iron(II) yield insoluble buff chelate and violet colour respectively at pH 2.5. The interference of these cations were completely masked by EDTA and phosphoric acid respectively before adding the reagent.

Experimental

1% solution of 2-hydroxy-4-methylpropiophenone oxime (HMPOX) was prepared in ethanol. Ammonium metavanadate was standardised gravimetrically. All the chemicals used were of reagent grade.

Determination of vanadium: A known volume of vanadium solution was transferred into a 250 ml beaker, diluted to about 100 ml with distilled water and the pH adjusted to 3.5 with sodium acetate solution. A small excess of oxime solution was added. A brown red precipitate of vanadium chelate was kept at room temperature (25-30°) for an hour. The precipitate was filtered off on a weighed sintered-glass crucible and washed with warm water followed by 30% ethanol to remove excess of the reagent. The chelate was dried to constant weight at 100-105° in air oven, cooled and weighed. Some of the representative results are given in Table-1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM pH 3.5

Vanadium taken (mg)	Wt. of complex (mg)	Vanadium found (mg)
6.1	52.6	6.09
12.2	105.0	12.16
24.4	211.0	24.41
36.6	317.0	36.67

It was found that the method gives good results in the pH range 2.5-4.0.

Determination of vanadium in presence of foreign ions: To study the effect of foreign ions on gravimetric determination of vanadium, 8-16 mg of various cations were added to a known volume of vanadium solution (12.2 mg vanadium) at pH 2.5-3.5 and estimations were carried out as mentioned above. It was observed that Hg(II), Cd(II), Mn(II), Zn(II), Ni(II), Co(II) do not interfere in the gravimetric determination of vanadium. The reagent gives insoluble buff chelate with Cu(II) at pH 2.5-9 and violet colour with Fe(III) at pH 2.5. Hence, these cations were completely masked by EDTA and phosphoric acid respectively before adding the reagent.

Separation and determination of vanadium and nickel: Definite volume of standard solutions of vanadium(V) and nickel(II) were mixed together and diluted to 200 ml, pH was adjusted to 2.5-3.0. A brown red vanadium chelate precipitated on adding ethanolic solution of the reagent was estimated gravimetrically as above. The filtrate and washings after removal of vanadium chelate were collected for the estimation of nickel. The volume was reduced to about 100 ml by heating. Its pH was adjusted to 5.5 and nickel was estimated gravimetrically as described in a previous communication⁸. The results are reproducible with an error $\pm 0.5\%$ for amount of vanadium ranging from 6.0 mg to 25.0 mg.

Composition and structure of vanadium chelate: On the basis of Job's continuous variations method applied to precipitation reactions and results of analysis for C, H, N and V, it was found that the metal and ligand are in the ratio of 1:2. Vanadium chelate was ignited to vanadium pentoxide to estimate its vanadium content. Composition of the chelate corresponds to VO(OH) (C₁₀H₁₂O₂N)₂.

Calc. C, 54.55; H, 5.68; N, 6.36; V₂O₅, 23.46%

Found C, 54.72; H, 5.56; N, 6.21; V₂O₅, 23.25%

Examination of the IR spectrum of the reagent showed strong bands at 3400 cm⁻¹ (phenolic OH), 2980 cm⁻¹ (OH of =N-OH), 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=N), 990 cm⁻¹ (N-O). Examination of the IR spectrum of the chelate shows that phenolic hydrogen is replaced by the metal because the strong peak at 3400 cm⁻¹ disappears in the chelate. The band at 2980 cm⁻¹ due to hydroxyl group of the oximino appears more or less at the same position in both the ligand and the chelate. The band appears at 1605 cm⁻¹ which can be very likely be assigned to ν C=N shifting down field, due to chelation. The ν N-O band appearing at 990 cm⁻¹ in the ligand shifts down field to 980 cm⁻¹ in the chelate. The position of ν N-O band has been confirmed by various workers^{9,10}. The band appearing at 1125 cm⁻¹ in the chelate may be assigned to V=O stretching mode. The complex formed is neutral in character. It can be extracted in organic solvents like CCl₄, CHCl₃, C₆H₆ etc.

The magnetic susceptibility, determined by the Gouy method, shows that the complex is diamagnetic. The molecular weight of the complex has been determined by cryoscopic method and shows the compound to be monomeric.

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Azine and Oxazine Dyes as Redox Indicators in Cerate Oxidimetry*

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DURING recent times, some azine and oxazine dyes have been reported as redox indicators in cerate oxidimetry¹⁻⁶. The present communication describes the results of our investigations on the use of an azine dye, Lissamine Blue BF (LBBF), and four oxazine dyes, Sevron Blue 5G (SB5G), Brilliant Cresyl Blue (BCB), Alizarin Blue S (ABS), and Resorcin Blue (RB) (Colour Index Nos. 50230, 51004, 51010, 51080 and 51400 respectively) as redox indicators in the titration of iron(II), arsenic(III), antimony(III), uranium(IV), vanadium(IV), molybdenum(V), hydroquinone and oxalic acid with ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) in perchloric acid medium. The advantages of these indicators are: relative cheapness, solubility in water and stability of the aqueous solutions.

Experimental

0.1 *N* solution of arsenic(III) was prepared from E. Merck 'pro analysi' grade arsenious oxide. 0.1 *N* solutions of iron(II), antimony(III), uranium(IV), vanadium(IV) (oxovanadium(IV)), molybdenum(V) (oxomolybdenum(V)), hydroquinone, oxalic acid and ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) (in 1.0 *M* perchloric acid) were prepared and standardised.

0.1% solutions of the dyes were prepared in deionised water from the following samples of dyes, without any further purification:—LBBF: Gurr; BCB: E. Merck; SB5G: du Pont; ABS and RB: Chroma. The dye solutions retained their indicator action for about six months.

General Procedure. Treat an aliquot of the reductant solution with enough 1:1 perchloric acid (70%), dilute to 50 ml and titrate with 0.1 *N* ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) solution employing the prescribed quantity of any one of the following indicators:—LBBF and BCB: 0.1 ml; SB5G and ABS: 0.15 ml; RB: 0.5 ml.

The conditions of titrations are given in Table 1 and the colour changes at the end points are:—LBBF: violet to pink (light pink to light yellow with V(IV)); SB5G: green (blue with arsenic(III)) to pink; BCB: green to pink; ABS: violet to colourless with Fe(II), pink to colourless with As(III) and oxalic acid and pale pink to pale yellow with hydroquinone; RB: pale pink to colourless.

The results obtained with all these indicators are in excellent agreement with those obtained by other standard methods; for example, the mean experimental errors for the different reductants, using LBBF as indicator, are as follows:—Fe(II): 0.16%; As(III): 0.10%; Sb(III): 0.09%; U(IV): 0.14%; V(IV): 0.15%; Mo(V): 0.05%; hydroquinone: 0.11%; oxalic acid: 0.06%.

LBBF, SB5G and BCB (but not ABS and RB) function satisfactorily in titrations involving 0.01 *N* solutions of the reductants with 0.01 *N* solutions of ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) also.

Indicator Corrections. An indicator correction of 0.04 ml is required while titrating with 0.01 *N* solutions of the oxidant whereas titrations involving 0.1 *N* solutions do not require any indicator correction.

Reverse Titrations. LBBF and BCB are the only suitable indicators in the reverse titrations, i.e., titrations of the cerate(IV) with the reductants, iron(II), molybdenum(V), and hydroquinone, under the same conditions of direct titrations. SB5G, ABS and RB are not suitable in titrations of these as well as other reductant systems.

Transition Potentials. The transition potentials, mV vs N.H.E., of the indicators in the iron(II)-cerate(IV) titration are:—LBBF: 950 ± 15; SB5G: 1185 ± 10; ABS: 825 ± 10; RB: 915 ± 15; BCB: 980 - 1040 (value reported by Sriramam⁴).

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